

PRECIOUS (PHET SIMULATION FOR REAL-WORLD ENGAGEMENT THROUGH CONCEPTUAL INTERACTIVE OUTCOMES FOR UNDERSTANDING IN SCIENCE)

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ABSTRACT

In the digital age, Physical Education Technology (PhET) simulations have become valuable tools for enhancing pupils' engagement and understanding of complex science concepts. This study focused on Grade 5 pupils of Laguilayan Central Elementary School, exploring their responses using PhET simulations in science lessons. Given the resource constraints in the school, it is crucial to understand how these digital tools influence pupils' motivation and learning outcomes in science education. The study employed a qualitative research design, utilizing thematic analysis of recorded statements from pupils after their engagement with PhET simulations in their lessons. These statements were analyzed to identify key themes related to pupils' engagement, motivation, understanding, and challenges. The findings revealed that PhET simulations significantly improved pupils' conceptual understanding, especially in abstract science concepts like circuits and electricity. The interactive nature of the simulations also increased pupils' engagement and motivation. However, technical difficulties were reported, and the study emphasized the need for better support and infrastructure, including improved internet access and teacher training, to fully optimize the use of PhET simulations in the classroom. To enhance the effectiveness of PhET simulations, it is recommended that schools invest in comprehensive teacher training, provide offline access to simulations, and improve technological infrastructure to ensure all students can benefit from this interactive learning tool.

Keywords: *PhET Simulations, Pupils' Engagement, Conceptual Understanding, Science Education, Technological Infrastructure*

INTRODUCTION

A dedicated science laboratory is essential for fostering pupils' critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills through hands-on learning that enhances understanding and retention of scientific concepts. However, challenges such as inadequate resources, outdated equipment, safety concerns, and lack of skilled personnel hinder effective laboratory use. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) emphasizes the importance of laboratory experiences in improving scientific literacy, with research showing that inquiry-based learning and well-designed experiments significantly enhance pupils' comprehension and application of knowledge (She et al., 2019; Prima et al., 2018). Socio-economic status, learning experiences, and familial support play crucial roles in shaping pupils' science proficiency, as highlighted by studies linking environmental awareness and academic success to these factors (Susongko & Afrizal, 2018; Bazán-Ramírez et al., 2021). These insights underscore the need for a holistic approach to science education that combines engaging laboratory experiences with supportive home environments to foster scientific literacy and overall academic achievement.

PhET simulations provide an interactive platform for pupils to explore complex scientific concepts, offering an effective alternative to traditional laboratories, especially in resource-constrained settings like the Philippines (Yunzal & Casinillo, 2020). By enabling pupils to perform virtual experiments and investigate concepts beyond the reach of limited physical resources, PhET simulations bridge gaps in science education (Danuarteu et al., 2023). This innovative approach not only enhances understanding but also cultivates critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for thriving in the 21st-century educational and professional landscape (Juwairiah et al., 2022).

Grade 5 pupils at Laguilayan Central Elementary School actively use PhET simulations to explore and understand scientific concepts interactively, enhancing their engagement and learning in STEM subjects. These tools provide valuable support in fostering scientific literacy and curiosity despite limited resources.

Research Questions

Building on previous research, the researcher developed an educational strategy that engaged pupils with the PhET Simulation. The researcher targeted the following research problems: Building on previous research, the researcher developed an educational strategy that engaged pupils with the PhET Simulation. The researcher targeted the following research problems:

1. How do PhET simulations impact Grade 5 pupils' understanding and conceptualization of science concepts?
2. In what ways do PhET simulations influence pupils' engagement, motivation, and active learning in science?
3. What challenges and support mechanisms are essential for maximizing the effectiveness of PhET simulations in the science classroom?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design using thematic analysis to explore the impact of PhET simulations on the scientific learning of Grade 5 pupils at Laguilayan Central Elementary School. The approach allowed for the identification and interpretation of patterns within the data, providing a deep understanding of the pupils' engagement with the simulations. Participants were selected from the Grade 5-Quezon section to capture diverse experiences. Pupils submitted recorded statements after using PhET in their science lessons, offering individual reflections on how the simulations influenced their learning. Observations were also conducted during PhET-integrated lessons to assess real-time engagement and behavioral responses.

The recorded statements and observations were systematically analyzed through thematic analysis. The process included familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, identifying and refining themes, and defining them in alignment with the study's objectives. This structured approach enabled the researcher to uncover key insights related to pupils' conceptual understanding, motivation, engagement, and challenges in using PhET. Direct quotes from pupils were used to support the themes and provide authentic evidence of their experiences. Overall, this methodology facilitated a meaningful exploration of how PhET simulations can enhance science learning, particularly in settings with limited access to traditional laboratory resources.

RESULTS

Through a rigorous process of thematic analysis, this study identified key themes that encapsulate the experiences of Grade 5 pupils using PhET simulations in their science learning. Seven emerging themes were synthesized from the pupils' responses, which were based on their individual experiences with the intervention.

The seven emerging themes are as follows: Improved Conceptual Understanding, Engagement and Motivation, Active and Experiential Learning, Curiosity, Confidence, and Independence, Need for Support and Accessibility, Collaboration and Social Interaction, and Barriers and Challenges. These themes reflect the diverse ways in which pupils interacted with the PhET simulations, shedding light on how this tool influenced their learning experiences. Through these findings, the study offers insights into the positive impact of PhET simulations on enhancing scientific understanding, pupils' engagement, and collaborative learning, while also addressing challenges and areas for improvement.

DISCUSSION

Emerging Theme 1. Cognitive and Conceptual Development

The following themes reflect the pupils' growth in their understanding of complex scientific concepts using PhET simulations. As learners engaged with the interactive tools, they were able to visualize and manipulate abstract scientific concepts that were previously difficult to grasp.

Clustered Theme 1-A: Improved Conceptual Understanding

Learners consistently emphasized that PhET simulations helped them understand abstract and complex science concepts, such as circuits and electricity. The visual and interactive nature of the simulations allowed them to grasp the relationships between components and see real-time effects, which deepened their conceptual learning. These insights suggest that PhET bridges the gap between theory and practice, especially in topics difficult to demonstrate without laboratory materials.

According to participants 3 and 6,
“Mas naiintindihan ko po ang konsepto ng kuryente kasi nakikita ko kung paano gumagana ang circuit kapag may binabago ako.” (Participant 3)
“I understand the concept of electricity better because I can see how the circuit works when I make changes.”
“Dati po, hindi ko gets ang pagdaloy ng kuryente, pero ngayon po, parang may larawan na sa isip ko.” (Participant 6)
“Before, I didn't understand how electricity flows, but now it's like I have a picture of it in my mind.”

Recent studies have shown that interactive simulations significantly enhance pupils' understanding of abstract and complex scientific concepts. Moore et al. (2020) found that pupils who used PhET simulations developed a more accurate and deeper conceptual grasp of scientific topics such as electricity, as simulations visually demonstrated the relationships among components in real-time. Similarly, Wieman and Adams (2018), the original developers of PhET, emphasized that these tools effectively bridge the gap between theory and practice, allowing pupils to visualize processes that are difficult to replicate in traditional classrooms. These findings affirm that simulations provide meaningful conceptual scaffolding, especially in resource-constrained environments lacking laboratory materials.

Clustered Theme 1-B: Active and Experiential Learning

Pupils reported that PhET simulations encouraged active participation. Instead of passively listening, they were able to manipulate variables, test outcomes, and make predictions—closely simulating the scientific method. This fostered deeper understanding and improved problem-solving skills, especially in the absence of physical lab tools.

According to participants 5 and 9,
“Nag-eeksperimento po kami. Tinitingnan namin kung ano ang mangyayari kapag binago namin ang settings.” (Participant 5)
“We do experiments. We observe what happens when we change the settings.”
“Parang ako na ang scientist kasi ako ang nagtatry ng iba’t ibang kombinasyon.” (Participant 9)
“I feel like I’m the scientist because I try different combinations myself.”

Experiential learning through simulations allows pupils to actively construct knowledge by experimenting and observing cause-and-effect relationships. Hasni et al. (2017) observed that simulations encourage pupils to manipulate variables, test hypotheses, and draw conclusions, thereby simulating authentic scientific inquiry. These findings support this study’s observations that pupils shifted from passive to active learning through PhET, helping them develop scientific thinking and critical reasoning skills in the absence of physical lab tools.

Emerging Theme 2: Engagement, and Independence

This highlights the pupils’ increased motivation and sense of autonomy during their use of PhET simulations. The interactive nature of the tool, which allowed pupils to experiment and explore science concepts actively, was a significant factor in making the learning process more engaging. This theme also touches on the pupils’ growing independence as they took ownership of their learning, solving problems and making discoveries on their own.

Clustered Theme 2-A: Engagement and Motivation

Many participants expressed increased interest, enjoyment, and motivation while using PhET simulations. The simulations’ game-like and interactive design made learning more appealing and fun, reducing boredom and passive listening. This type of engagement is crucial in low-resource settings where science instruction is often limited to textbook discussions.

According to participants 4 and 7,
“Masaya po gamitin ang PhET kasi parang laro pero natututo kami. Hindi po boring katulad ng ibang lesson.” (Participant 4)
“Using PhET is fun because it feels like a game, but we still learn. It’s not boring like other lessons.”
“Gusto ko pong ulit-ulitin kasi bawat pindot, may bago akong natututunan.” (Participant 7)
“I want to keep using it again and again because every click teaches me something new.”

Interactive environments such as PhET simulations also boost pupils’ motivation and interest in learning science. According to Akaygun and Aslan-Tutak (2019), pupils exposed to game-like simulations reported higher engagement, enjoyment, and enthusiasm toward science lessons. These simulations helped reduce passive learning by making the learning environment more dynamic and fun. Such findings resonate with

those of the current study, which observed that the visual and interactive nature of PhET simulations captured learners' attention and minimized classroom boredom—an important outcome in low-resource schools where textbook-only instruction can be disengaging.

Clustered Theme 2-B: Curiosity, Confidence, and Independence

PhET sparked curiosity among pupils, encouraging them to go beyond what was taught. Some shared how their confidence improved as they explored the tool and figured things out independently. They saw mistakes not as failures but as part of learning, fostering resilience and autonomy.

According to participants 2 and 10,
“Na-curious po ako kaya pinindot ko lahat ng button para malaman ko kung para saan sila.” (Participant 2)
“I got curious, so I clicked all the buttons to find out what they're for.”
“Nung una po nahirapan ako, pero nung naintindihan ko na, mas naging confident ako gamitin ito.” (Participant 10)
“At first, I struggled, but when I understood it, I became more confident using it.”

Studies have highlighted how simulations contribute to learners' curiosity and build their confidence in scientific exploration. Rutten, van Joolingen, and van der Veen (2021) found that pupils using digital simulations became more autonomous and resilient, overcoming learning challenges through trial and error. They reported that such learners displayed increased initiative, persistence, and interest in delving into science topics beyond the surface level. These findings align with participants' reflections in the current study, where learners became more self-directed and confident after repeated interactions with the PhET simulations.

Emerging Theme 3: Challenges, Support, and Collaboration

This focuses on the obstacles pupils faced while using the PhET simulations and the support they needed to overcome them. Some pupils experienced technical difficulties, such as poor internet connectivity or unfamiliarity with the platform, which hindered their ability to fully engage with the simulations. Despite these challenges, pupils emphasized the importance of support from teachers and peers. Collaboration played a key role, with many pupils helping one another navigate the simulations and share their discoveries.

Clustered Theme 3-A: Need for Support and Accessibility

Despite its effectiveness, pupils encountered technical issues such as device limitations, slow internet, and difficulty understanding simulations without guidance. These findings show that teacher support, device accessibility, and localized content are essential for maximizing PhET's benefits.

According to participants 8 and 1,
“Minsan po hindi ko gets kung ano ang gagawin kasi walang nagsasabi. Sana may gabay po bago gamitin.” (Participant 8)
“Sometimes I don’t get what to do because no one explains. I wish there was guidance before using it.”
“Nagla-lag po yung cellphone ko kaya hindi ako nakasunod agad.” (Participant 1)
“My phone lagged, so I couldn’t follow right away.”

Despite their benefits, simulations like PhET face implementation barriers in low-tech settings. Cruz and Kalolo (2019) found that limited access to stable internet, digital devices, and teacher preparedness hindered effective technology integration in rural schools. These constraints mirror the challenges raised by participants in this study. As a response, Kabakci Yurdakul and Coklar (2022) recommend targeted teacher training and wider access to offline or low-bandwidth tools to maximize the potential of simulations in marginalized contexts.

Clustered Theme 3-B: Barriers and Challenges

Some pupils expressed anxiety, confusion, and cognitive overload during their first encounters with PhET. This emphasizes the need for clear scaffolding, orientation, and gradual exposure to new tools to ensure positive learning experiences.

According to participants 12 and 5,
“Noong una po, nakakalito. Hindi ko alam kung saan magsisimula.” (Participant 12)
“At first, it was confusing. I didn’t know where to start.”
“Medyo nahirapan ako kasi ang daming pwede pindutin.” (Participant 5)
“I had a hard time because there were too many buttons to press.”

Finally, while pupils generally responded positively to simulations, some studies noted initial frustration and cognitive overload. Rutten et al. (2021) emphasized that unfamiliar interfaces and lack of guidance can result in anxiety among pupils, particularly during first-time use. This supports the current study’s finding that learners needed structured support during early exposure to simulations to prevent confusion and maximize the learning experience. These results suggest that gradual onboarding and teacher facilitation are crucial when introducing new digital tools.

Clustered Theme 3-C: Collaboration and Social Interaction

The use of PhET simulations encouraged learners to collaborate, ask for help, and share discoveries with peers. These social interactions contributed to collective understanding and a sense of classroom community.

According to participants 5 and 9,
“Tinuruan po ako ng kaklase ko kung paano gamitin. Tapos po nagtulungan kami.” (Participant 11)
“My classmate taught me how to use it. Then we helped each other.”

“Mas natuto po ako kasi sabay naming ine-explore ng seatmate ko.” (Participant 6)
“I learned more because my seatmate and I explored it together.”

Technology-enhanced learning environments can promote collaboration among peers. Lin and Lan (2019) discovered that pupils using simulations were more likely to engage in peer discussions, share discoveries, and support each other’s learning. The collaborative aspects of these environments created a sense of classroom community, encouraging social learning. The present study also observed that PhET use led to peer-to-peer assistance, reinforcing the social constructivist perspective that learning occurs through interaction and dialogue.

Conclusions

Based on the objectives of this study, the findings confirm that PhET simulations significantly contribute to improving Grade 5 pupils’ understanding of science concepts at Laguilayan Central Elementary School. First, pupils responded positively to the use of PhET, demonstrating increased engagement, motivation, and interest in learning science. The interactive design of the simulations helped them visualize abstract concepts, promoting better cognitive and conceptual understanding. Second, the simulations served as a catalyst for independent exploration and active learning, empowering pupils to think critically and make sense of scientific phenomena through hands-on digital experiences.

However, challenges such as limited internet connectivity and lack of access to devices revealed the need for stronger technical support and infrastructure. Ensuring that both pupils and teachers are well-prepared to use PhET effectively is vital to achieving the intended learning outcomes. This study concludes that with proper integration, training, and support, PhET simulations can become a powerful teaching tool, even in resource-constrained environments. Their use in science instruction not only enhances conceptual learning but also cultivates a more engaging and learner-centered classroom experience.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, several recommendations can be made to enhance the use of PhET simulations in science education.

1. To ensure all pupils can benefit from PhET simulations, schools should prioritize providing adequate technological resources, including computers, tablets, and reliable internet connections.
2. To maximize the effectiveness of PhET simulations, teachers should receive proper training in using the tool.
3. Given that pupils expressed a preference for collaborative learning, it is recommended to incorporate group-based activities where pupils can work together, share discoveries, and discuss their findings.
4. To mitigate the technical challenges encountered by pupils, it is important to provide consistent technical support and ensure that both pupils and teachers are familiar with the PhET platform.

5. Regular reflective practices, such as journaling or group discussions, should be incorporated into lessons to encourage pupils to reflect on their learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author affirms that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. Ethical approval was obtained before the commencement of the research, and informed consent was acquired from all respondents involved. No specific funding was received for this research from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit organizations. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable

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